

Development of Metacognition-Based Multiliteration Learning Models to Improve Students' Creative Writing Skills

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Abstract

This research is based on problems related to the application of metacognition-based multiliteracy learning models to improve students' creative writing skills, which so far have not activated students' metacognitive abilities. The purpose of the study was to find a valid, practical and effective learning model to improve students' creative writing skills. The methodology used is the Plomp model development research. The research was conducted in elementary schools in Deli Serdang Regency. The products produced are model books, lesson plans, teacher books, student books and student worksheets that have been validated by experts and practitioners and then field trials are carried out.

Introduction

Writing is a language skill that aims to express ideas, ideas, and feelings in writing. By writing students will experience a thinking process to express their ideas and ideas widely. The process of writing is closely related to the factors of developing creative thinking, based on the underlying experience. This experience can be obtained through reading, listening and discussing. In addition, writing is also a productive and expressive activity.

To achieve these expectations, the teacher factor in learning activities is required to implement and meet the demands of the curriculum as an important component in the learning process. But in reality there are still teachers who are less creative in developing learning models that can improve students' writing skills.

One of the learning models that can be applied by teachers is the multiliteracy learning model. Multiliteracy learning model is learning that emphasizes reading, logic, research, speaking, and writing to seek and form a complex understanding of knowledge content related to certain scientific fields (Conachie et-al, 2010). Mckee and Ogle. (2005) describes the multiliteracy learning model placing the ability to read, write, listen, and the ability to criticize, analyze and evaluate information from various sources in various disciplines and the ability to communicate that information.

Students' metacognition as an internal factor is a factor that is a student which also becomes important to study in improving students' writing skills, this is confirmed by Eggen and Kauchak (2009), Williams and Atkins (2009) that metacognition can help students understand and regulate their own learning process so that they become independent students. Several studies also show the important role of metacognition in learning including: D'Souza (2013) Iskandar (2014) Erdogan (2017) which shows metacognition can help students carry out and complete their learning tasks more effectively.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Abidin (2015) explains that the multiliteracy learning model is a learning model that optimizes multiliteracy skills (reading, writing, speaking, and using IT) and 21st century competencies ((1) creativity and innovation, (2) critical thinking, problem solving, and decision making, (3) metacognition, (4) communication, (5) collaboration, (6) information literacy, (7) information and communication technology literacy, (8) citizenship, (9) life and career, and (10) personal and social responsibility, including awareness of competence and culture) in creating a better learning situation. The multiliteracy model as a democratic learning model in which students can work together, discuss, exchange ideas, give and receive friends' opinions, correct each other's work, and help each other in their learning (Supriyadi, 2015).

The functions of multiliteracy learning are 1) generating understanding or knowledge that students already have; (2) guide the process of acquiring knowledge that students already have; (3) develop or enrich students' concrete understanding of the knowledge and skills they have learned; (4) become the main means for channeling, demonstrating, and demonstrating the understanding and skills gained from learning activities; (5) become a procedure for proactive, motivated, and creative learning creators (Abidin, 2015).

Morocco (2008) explains that the components of multiliteracy learning are: objectives, important questions, learning cycle, learning resources, learning assessment, and output components. Furthermore, Morocco (2008) explains the syntax of the multiliterate learning model, namely: (1) orientation on creative texts, (2) awareness of creative writing, (3) generating ideas and creative writing, (4) Examining creative ideas and texts, and (5) presenting creative text

Metacognition was first introduced by Flavell in 1976 (Desmita, 2010). Fauziana (2008) explains that metacognition is an awareness of students, consideration, and controlling or monitoring their own strategies and cognitive processes. Wellman (2008) states that metacognition is a form of cognition, or a second or more level thinking process that involves controlling cognitive activity. Livingstone (1997) states metacognition as a thinking ability where the object of thinking is the thought process that occurs in oneself. Husamah and Yanur (2011) explain metacognition is a word related to what is known about him as an individual who learns and how he controls and adjusts his behavior.

Cohors-Fresenborg and Kaune in Santoso (2008) summarize the components of metacognition into three activities carried out in answering questions, consisting of planning, monitoring, and reflection. Meanwhile, Brown (2015) specifically limits the four components of metacognition, namely: planning, monitoring, evaluating, and revising. Livingstone (1997) suggests that metacognition includes two components, namely metacognitive knowledge, and metacognitive experiences or regulation.

Sjutz in Andreson (2010) states that metacognitive steps to control cognitive activity are: the planning process, the monitoring process, and the reflecting process. The same thing is explained by Khoe (2015: 210) that there are three stages of metacognition learning strategies, namely the conscious stage of the learning process, the stage of planning learning, and the stage of monitoring and learning reflection.

Creative writing can be said as an expression of a way of thinking in expressing ideas or unusual ideas so that they can be poured into different works (Yunus (2015).Ogilvie(2012) explained that creative writing activities allow the brain's natural learning system to occur. Munandar (2009) in creative writing there are four criteria that need to be considered, namely fluency), flexibility, originality and elaboration.

RESEARCH METHOD

The type of research used is development research by adopting the model from Plomp with the development stages of the initial investigation stage, design stage, realization stage and evaluation and revision stage. This development research aims to develop a metacognition-based multiliteracy learning model. The place of research was carried out in elementary schools in Deli Serdang Regency with the research subjects being fifth grade elementary school students. The data collection instruments used were validation sheets, observation sheets and learning outcomes tests.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Result

The development of a metacognition-based multiliterate learning model begins with the following initial investigation activities: the implementation of Indonesian language learning that is carried out and the implementation of the learning model carried out at the Al-Hijrah Laut Integrated Islamic Elementary School, Lautdandang Deliserdang which is used as the rationale for developing a learning model, and the results of pre-school education. -trials on the use of metacognitive aspects in learning Indonesian in class V of Al-Hijrah Laut Integrated Islamic Elementary School, Dandang Deli Serdang.

The second stage of the development of the learning model is the initial design of the components needed for the implementation of the learning model, namely: the initial design of the metacognition-based multiliteracy learning model, the initial design of the learning tools, namely the lesson plan, teacher's book, student book, appropriate student worksheets. with a metacognition-based multiliteracy learning model, and the design of the instruments used to obtain data in the development process of the metacognition-based multiliteracy learning model and the required learning tools.

The third stage is the realization stage of the development of metacognition-based multiliterate learning models including syntax, social systems, reaction principles, support systems and instructional impacts and the impact of accompaniment of metacognition-based multiliterate learning models.

The fourth stage is evaluation and revision, this stage aims to consider the quality of the design developed and make sustainable decisions based on the results of careful consideration. Evaluation includes the process of systematically collecting, processing and analyzing information. This is done to assess the quality of the selected problem solving. This is followed by revision activities and then back to designing activities, and so on. This cycle is a feedback cycle. Evaluation and revision activities can occur repeatedly and stop after obtaining the desired results.

The recapitulation of metacognition-based multiliteracy learning validation is listed in Table 1 below:

Table 1. Learning Model Validation Recapitulation

No	Aspect	Average Score	Criteria
1	Contents	3.61	Very Valid
2	construct	3.62	Very Valid
Average		3.61	Very Valid

Referring to Table 1, it can be seen that the validation of the metacognition-based multiliteracy learning model obtained an average score of 3.61 and was in the very valid category.

The recapitulation of the validation of the metacognition-based multiliterate learning model learning tools is listed in Table 2 below:

Table 2. Learning Tool Validation Recapitulation

No	Learning Media	Average Score	Criteria
1	RPP	3.72	Very Valid
2	Teacher's Book	3.77	Very Valid
3	Student Book	3.74	Very Valid
4	LKPD	3.64	Very Valid
Average		3.72	Very Valid

Referring to Table 2, it can be seen that the results of the validation of the metacognition-based multiliteracy learning model learning tools obtained an average score of 3.72 with a very valid category.

A recapitulation of the implementation of the metacognition-based multiliteracy learning model is listed in Table 3 below:

Table 3. Recapitulation of the Implementation of the Learning Model

No	Aspect	Average Score	Criteria
1	Syntax	3.73	Very high
2	Social System	3.63	Very high
3	Reaction Principle	3.72	Very high
Average		3.69	Very high

Referring to Table 3, it can be seen that the recapitulation of the implementation of the metacognition-based multiliteracy learning model obtained an average score of 3.69 with a very high category.

The recapitulation of the validation of the effectiveness of the metacognition-based multiliteracy learning model is listed in Table 4 below:

Table 4. Recapitulation of the Validation of the Effectiveness of the Learning Model

No	Aspect	Average Score	Criteria
1	Student learning outcomes	3.60	Very effective
2	Student And Teacher Activities	3.52	Very effective
3	Teacher's Ability to Manage Learning	3.72	Very effective
4	Student and Teacher Response	3.57	Very effective
Average		3.60	Very effective

Referring to Table 4, it can be seen that the recapitulation of the effectiveness of the metacognition-based multiliteracy learning model obtained an average score of 3.60 with a very effective category.

The recapitulation of the implementation of the metacognition-based multiliteracy learning model is listed in Table 5 below:

Table 5. Recapitulation of the Implementation of the Learning Model

No	Trial Stage	Average Score	Criteria
1	First	2.76	Currently
2	Second	3.26	Tall
3	Third	3.62	Very high

Referring to Table 5, it can be seen that the recapitulation of the implementation of the metacognition-based multiliteracy learning model in the first stage of the trial with a score of 2.76 in the medium category, the second stage with a score of 3.26 in the high category and the third stage with a score of 3.62 in the very high category.

The recapitulation of the effectiveness of the metacognition-based multiliteracy learning model in improving students' creative writing skills is listed in Table 6 below:

Table 6. Recapitulation of the Effectiveness of the Learning Model In Improving Creative Writing Skills

No	Trial Stage	Average Score	Criteria
1	First	0.65	Currently
2	Second	0.75	Tall
3	Third	0.77	Tall

Referring to Table 6, it can be seen the recapitulation of the effectiveness of the metacognition-based multiliteracy learning model in improving creative writing skills in the first stage of the trial with a score of 0.65 in the medium category, the second stage with a score of 0.75 in the high category and the third stage with a score of 0.77 in the high category.

The summary of the teacher's ability to manage the metacognition-based multiliteracy learning model is listed in Table 7 below:

Table 7. Recapitulation of Teacher Ability Trials to Manage Learning

No	Trial Stage	Average Score	Criteria
1	First	3.03	Good
2	Second	3.28	Good
3	Third	3.65	Very good

Referring to Table 7, it can be seen the recapitulation of the teacher's ability to manage the metacognition-based multiliteracy learning model in the first stage of the trial with a score of 3.03 in the good category, the second stage with a score of 3.28 in the good category and the third stage with a score of 3.65 in the very good category.

2. Discussion

The results of the validation carried out by experts and education practitioners in general on model books are divided into: (1) content validation with an average score of 3.61 very valid categories, and (2) construction validation with an average score of 3.62 very high categories. This means that the model book of the learning model product The metacognition-based multiliteracy developed reflects the level of validity for use. But of course, by accommodating suggestions for improvement submitted by experts and educational practitioners

The developed model book can be used by teachers in implementing Indonesian language learning. This model book provides detailed explanations that teachers can guide in implementing learning in the classroom. The urgency of this model book as a teacher guide is in line with Majid's (2005) explanation that all forms of materials are used to assist teachers in carrying out learning activities. The material in question can be in the form of written material or unwritten material.

Validation carried out by experts and practitioners on the learning implementation plan of the learning model metacognition-based multiliteracy showed an average score of 3.72 very valid categories. The results of the validation carried out by education experts and practitioners on teacher books showed an average of 3.77 very valid categories. The results of the validation carried out by experts and education practitioners in general on student books showed an average score of 3.74 very valid categories. The results of the validation carried out

by experts and design practitioners in general on student worksheets show an average score of 3.64 very valid categories.

The results of expert and practical validation of education on learning tools, namely learning implementation plans, teacher books, student books and student worksheets which show a very valid category, it means that the learning model learning tools The metacognition-based multiliteracy developed reflects the level of validity for use.

The results of practicality trials in this case are related to the implementation of the learning model metacognition-based multiliteracy which was carried out in the first trial showed a score of 2.76 and was in the moderate implementation category. Meanwhile, in the second trial, the practical achievement score of the metacognition-based multiliteracy learning model implemented was 3.26 in the high implementation category. Furthermore, in the third trial, the score for the practicality of the metacognition-based multiliteracy learning model implemented was 3.62, the category of implementation was very high.

This level of accessibility can be achieved due to the availability of model books, teacher books, student books, lesson plans and student worksheets to assist teachers in implementing learning models. metacognition-based multiliteracy in the classroom because there are guidelines. This is in line with the assertion of AECT (1986) that planned learning resources (by design) are all learning resources that are specifically designed as components of the learning system to provide directed and formal learning facilities and are applied for learning purposes. The AECT statement above is supported by the explanation of Siregar and Nara (2010) that designed learning resources can provide a more concrete and direct learning experience and can provide accurate information in solving educational problems.

The effectiveness of the metacognition-based multiliterate learning model in terms of four aspects, namely: (1) student learning outcomes, (2) achievement of the ideal percentage of time for student and teacher activities, (3) teacher's ability to manage learning, and (4) student and teacher responses to components and Learning Activities. These four aspects indicate that the category is very effective so it can be interpreted that the metacognition-based multiliteracy learning model is effective for improving students' creative writing skills in the aspect of student and teacher responses to learning components and activities.

The application of metacognition-based multiliteracy learning model in Indonesian language learning has an impact on the level of students' creative writing skills. This is evident from the difference in student achievement scores in the first trial with an average score of 0.65 in the medium category, student achievement in the second trial with an average score of 0.75 in the high category, while student achievement in the third trial with an average score of 0.77 high category. This is understandable because through metacognition-based multi-literacy learning students practice individually and in groups to write through the stages of exercises through learning activities and working on student worksheets so that by themselves students have better writing skills.

The improvement of students' writing skills can increase because through the stages of learning activities in the multiliterate learning model, students can train creative writing skills, in this case Martin as quoted by Mahmudi (2010) that creative thinking ability is the ability to generate new ideas or ways to produce a product. Creative thinking is the ability to think with regard to the ability to produce or develop something new, which is something different from the ideas produced by most people.

The ability of teachers to manage multiliteracy learning models based on metacognition in the first trial obtained an average score of 3.03 in the good category, while in the second trial with an average score of 3.28 in the good category, then in the third trial with an average score of 3.65 very good category. Thus, it can be interpreted that the metacognition-based multiliterate learning model is easy to understand and apply to teachers so that it can be implemented properly.

The teacher's role in managing learning by applying a metacognition-based multiliterate learning model properly will lead to the achievement of student learning outcomes. This is reinforced by previous research conducted by Fisher (2008) on *Thinking About Thinking: Developing Metacognition in Children*. Research findings suggest that meta-teaching strategies can help mediate children's metacognitive skills, helping stimulate children's metacognitive thinking. This article refers to research being conducted in schools in one London borough to improve achievement in thinking and learning through the development of students' metacognition, and (2) Demerdash (2010) on *The Development of an Instrument to Measure Geometric Creativity*. The research findings put forward the conclusion that there is no doubt that students can learn and develop their creative potential, if we use an appropriate program that successfully teaches them the skills of creativity and its operation. However, to measure the effectiveness of such a program, we need an instrument of creativity value.

CONCLUSION

The entire set of metacognition-based multiliterate learning models has been validated by educational experts and practitioners, the results showing high criteria so that the learning model product is feasible to use.

Furthermore, the metacognition-based multiliterate learning model has a level of practicality, and effectiveness to improve students' creative writing skills. The level of students' creative writing skills, the ability of teachers to manage learning well, and student learning activities during the learning process have increased.

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